

**O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY VA O'RTA
MAX'SUS TA'LIM VAZIRLIGI
A. QODIRIY NOMIDAGI JIZZAX DAVLAT
PEDAGOGIKA INSTITUTI**

**CHET TILLARINI O'RGATISHNING TURLICHA
YONDASHUVLARI: MUAMMO VA YECHIMLAR**
Xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya materiallari 2021 yil 1-iyun

**Proceedings of the International Scientific-Practical
Conference**
**DIFFERENT APPROACHES TO FOREIGN LANGUAGE
TEACHING: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS**
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Mazkur ilmiy-amaliy ma’ruza tezislar to’plamida xorijiy mamlakatlar hamda mamlakatimiz turli yo’nalish va mutaxassislik olimlari, OTMning professor-o’qituvchilari, ilmiy tadqiqot institutlari va markazlarining ilmiy hodimlari, tadqiqotchilari, magistr va talabalarning ilmiy – tadqiqot ishlari natijalari mujassamlashgan.

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**APPLICATION OF THE THEORY OF FANTASTIC WORLDS TO ISAAC
ASIMOV'S "THE BICENTENNIAL MAN"**

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Abstract. This article is aimed to reveal how smoothly and accurately the theory and classification of textual worlds, adopted in cognitive poetics, fits the fantastic world created by famous American science fiction writer Isaac Asimov on the pages of his novelette "The Bicentennial Man".

Key words: science fiction, Asimov, "Bicentennial Man", the theory of textual worlds, fantastic world, cognitive poetics.

Science fiction is of particular interest not only to literary scholars and critics, but also to researchers working in the field of cognitive linguistics and cognitive poetics. This can be explained by the fact that science fiction creates fictional (alternative) worlds that are both *alien* and *recognizable* [1, 13] to readers, and the "alienation" of these images can shed light on the process of creating mental constructions, which are called "mental spaces" in cognitive linguistics [2, 66]. When science fiction writers, including Isaac Asimov, create their fictional worlds, they rely on existing concepts of *alien* and *recognizable*. In fact, a key feature of science fiction texts is the creation of new worlds. In the sphere of science fiction and its subgenres, the classification of textual worlds, developed by Andreeva [6], is well-known and quite widely implemented; and according to this classification textual worlds of literary work can be subdivided into *quasi-real world* and *fantastic world*. *Quasi-real worlds* are the worlds in which the readers can find themselves (with the amendment that these worlds are still fictional and can be described just as similar to real, but non-existent places, objects and phenomena). *Fantastic worlds* are the worlds in which the readers cannot find themselves according to the laws of their own world (that is, these are situations of time travel, interstellar travel, and many other popular science fiction topics). The fantastic textual world has a fantastic *deixis*, that is, the following different from the real aspects: place, time or characters. Note, that *deixis* is the use of general words and phrases to refer to a specific time and/or place in context, e.g., the words "tomorrow", "there", etc. Words are deictic if their semantic meaning is fixed but their denoted meaning varies depending on time and/or place. At the same time, attachment to the reader's world is necessary, from our point of view, since, as Todorov notes, a reader makes a decision about the fantastic nature of what is happening on the basis of knowledge about his world [7]. It is assumed that the reader will experience some difficulties trying to imagine himself in a new world, about which he knows little. But this is the motivation that attracts readers to turn to the

genre of science fiction – what Suvin calls “cognitive estrangement” [4, 7]. Alternatively, in addition to quasi-real and fantastic worlds, *quasi-real worlds with fantastic elements* can also be distinguished [3, 39]. They include worlds that are more likely to quasi-real ones (that is, the reader as a whole does not experience problems imagining himself in the described world), with the exception of one or two fantastic assumptions. They may not strongly influence the plot of the work, but they already distinguish the literary work from the others of more realistic genres.

“The Bicentennial Man” is a science-fiction novelette by Isaac Asimov about a 200-year-old robot. It won the *Hugo Award* and *Nebula Award* for best science fiction novelette in 1976. NDR is a humanoid robot acquired by a rich family. They change its name to the more familiar Andrew as it has a positronic brain and takes care of the two daughters and one in particular loves him too much. The robot calls her Little Miss. First, Andrew starts to make art, then he starts taking conscience and wants more freedom and rights. The owner of the robot dies. The robot cannot cry but it feels very sad about it. Little Miss grows to adulthood and helps the robot to gain its rights. The robot goes to mechanical men to acquire some upgrades. It then goes to an amateur roboticist and he makes him an upgrade to look like a real man. Now, readers can name the robot as “he”. Andrew meets a female robot which he was searching. He disappoints because she is totally artificial. As Little Miss dies, he is very depressed about it. He later decides to end his life. He goes to the roboticist again and tells him to change his brain in a way that it can die like a human being. He also gains “a more humane” mind. He is considered human, at last, by people and he dies at 200 years of age, honoring the name of the novelette.

Andreeva’s classification is best applied to works like “Harry Potter” by J. Rowling, “The Wonderful Wizard of Oz” by L. Frank Baum or “The Chronicles of Narnia” by C.S. Lewis, in which the opposition of the fantastic and the non-fantastic is initially present: the world of wizards and people without magical abilities (Rowling); the magic land of Oz and Kansas (L. Frank Baum); the magical world of Narnia and London (C.S. Lewis). It is interesting that in works of a more sci-fi orientation, a bias is rather manifested in the direction of fantastic or worlds with elements of the fantastic. For example, in the novelette “Bicentennial Man” by Isaac Asimov, the only cases of quasi-real worlds fall on those moments when the fantastic essence of what is happening is not obvious from the description, and then these moments do not last long and soon change to fantastic worlds or worlds with elements of the fantastic, which is already explained by the author’s style [5, 44].

The typology of textual worlds in “The Bicentennial Man” can be represented as follows: 1) *quasi-real worlds*: the house of the Martins; Andrew’s visit to the surgeon; 2) *quasi-real worlds with the inclusion of fantastic elements*: the house of the Martins and the robot Andrew; robotic surgeon’s office; regional office of US Robots & Mechanical Men; robot trial; Feingold Law Firm (later: Feingold & Martin); the world of the near future (the beginning of the novelette); 3) *fantastic worlds*: the Moon; the world of the distant future (the end of the novelette).

As quasi-real worlds, as mentioned above, we identified textual worlds without any fantastic elements in the deixis of passages. Quasi-real worlds with the inclusion of fantastic elements became worlds that differ from simply quasi-real by the inclusion of fantastic characters (this was mainly deixis of characters). If, in addition to this, there were also fantastic elements in other deictic categories, in particular, the deixis of time (indication of the distant future) or place (mention of an earthly colony on the Moon).

As you can see, the novelette “The Bicentennial Man” contains examples of all the aforementioned types of textual worlds, and here there is a predominance of quasi-real worlds

with the inclusion of fantastic elements, while two simply quasi-real worlds and fantastic ones were singled out in this work. This may seem somewhat surprising for a fantastic work, however, if you look at the volume of text fragments that make up quasi-real worlds, you will notice that the description of such worlds takes up a small part of the work, in contrast to quasi-real worlds with the inclusion of fantastic elements and fantastic worlds. If we look at the distribution of these different worlds in chronological and plot planes, then the distribution of the types of worlds from quasi-real to fantastic (with a few exceptions) will be noticeable. Such a distribution of worlds, on the one hand, corresponds to the chronological development of actions in the story: events in it take place over 200 years, and those worlds that were theoretically available to the reader at the very beginning, more and more move away from him over time in the work. On the other hand, the plot distribution of textual worlds, starting with quasi-real ones, facilitates the reader's perception of the text and its "entry" into the textual worlds.

In the fictional realities of the fantastic world, much attention is paid to the objects of external reality – new forms of energy, vehicles, weapons, etc., exotic clothes, plants and animals. etc. Once they appear in one story or novel, they can jump into the thesaurus of all science fiction and even other genres and styles. Such are the neologisms like "robot", "space station", "solar battery", "spacesuit", "shuttle" etc. The conceptual realities of fictional worlds remain behind the scenes. This is understandable, since science fiction writers are actively inventing new words to denote external realities, and the internal sphere of personalities and fictional communities belonging to other worlds and times is described through the same system of concepts as the internal sphere of a person in non-fantastic literature. All the same concepts, called by the same words, are used: good, evil, justice, betrayal, etc.

The peculiarity of Isaac Asimov's "The Bicentennial Man" is that the author offers the reader both scientific or not entirely scientific assumptions, and then builds around them that picture of the new fantastic world, which will develop with the existence of this convention. That is, it builds a slightly different model of reality, scientific, technological, cultural, behavioral, and social. Thus, the article analyzed the modeling of social processes (science, art, culture, technical achievements), so, future research can be focused on the modeling of consciousness in the works of science fiction in general, and in the works of Isaac Asimov, in particular.

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